

What Is Secularism? What Is Sharia?

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Abstract

Secularism stands as the foremost revolution implemented by Gazi Mustafa Kemal Ataturk subsequent to the expulsion of our adversaries from our territory. All these revolutions are collectively interconnected. He not only defended our country

and nation from foreign attacks, but also implemented a series of interconnected and transformative changes. This was done to guarantee the perpetual stability of the nation he rescued, preventing it from ever being in a vulnerable position again in all aspects. Additionally, it aimed to maintain the enduring stability of the republican rule, which was established on the values of personal freedom, rights, and equality. Due to his revolutionary nature and the unattainability of his military genius, Ataturk has secured a prestigious and honorable place in the records of world history. He has the highest ecclesiastical and military ranks, including veteran and field marshal. The republican government is defined by the autonomy of society via assemblies composed of individuals elected by the people. Consequently, secularism is a crucial element of the republican system. This kind of governance occurs when the legislative, executive, and judicial parts of government are maintained as separate entities. The National Assembly is tasked with the role of

enacting legislation, which essentially means creating laws. Both the executive branch and the judicial branch are bound by these laws. In other terms, the laws enacted by the populace are accountable for executing social activities inside a republican government.

Key Words: *Mustafa Kemal Atatürk, Secularism, Sharia, Turkish Revolution*

Introduction

The most significant of the revolutions implemented by Gazi Mustafa Kemal Atatürk, after the expulsion of our collective adversaries, is the establishment of secularism. He not only defended our country and nation against enemy aggression, but also implemented a series of interconnected and transformative reforms to prevent the recurrence of such dire circumstances in all aspects. These reforms aimed to establish a lasting republican regime founded on the principles of personal freedom, rights, and equality.

Atatürk, who attained the highest religious and military grades of veteran and field marshal, secured a prominent and esteemed position in global history due to his innovative approach and exceptional military expertise. Secularism is a fundamental component of the republican system, since the republican system entails the autonomous rule of society by elected assemblies. This form of governance is characterized by the division of powers among the legislative, executive, and judicial branches.

The National Assembly is responsible for the enactment of legislation, which involves the process of creating laws. These laws control the executive and judiciary. Put simply, under a republican system, social matters are governed by legislation enacted by individuals.

FIRST STEPS TOWARDS SECULARISM, THE WAR FOR POWER AND THE FIRST DIFFERENCES: THE WAR OF THE KING AND THE POPE

Nevertheless, the concept and implementation of democracy, which had significant sway in Ancient Greece, did not experience the same level of excitement

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in subsequent eras and was almost disregarded. During the Middle Ages, democracy as a form of governance was no longer a topic of debate. Instead, the idea of "sacred sovereignty" became the central focus of discussions about the legitimacy of kingdoms. This principle revolved around the relationship between rulers and the ruled. The governmental authority, which was first justified by religion and other holy aspects, eventually sought to emancipate itself from the influence and control of religion and its representatives. During the Middle Ages, the power struggle was mostly influenced by the concept of the two swords theory. According to the doctrine of two swords, there are two powers: one pertaining to worldly matters, known as *gladius temporalis*, and the other pertaining to spiritual matters, known as *gladius spiritualis*. The origin of this contention may be traced back to a letter delivered by Pope Galesius, who held the papacy from 494 to 496, to the Eastern Roman Emperor Anastasios. In his letter, Pope Galesius included biblical references (Luke 22/38) to support his argument. (Kelsen, 2007, page 164).

Quillet will provide a concise summary of this situation:

Both swords, one representing earthly authority and the other representing spiritual authority, are ultimately under the control of the church; the spiritual sword is wielded by the clergy, while the temporal sword is wielded by the king and knights, with the consent and authorization of the clergy. This implies that the sword should be submissive to spiritual authority, and temporal power should be subordinate to spiritual authority. (Quoted by Ağaoğulları, 1997, p. 21).

Hence, the Roman Church asserts its supremacy over other authority by asserting that spiritual power not only encompasses but also surpasses temporal power. This argument is supported by the notion of *plenitudo potestatis*, which will be further discussed. Over time, the conflict between the popes and monarchs, who symbolize the religious and political domains respectively, escalates into a more intense and aggressive confrontation. Indeed, these disputes, which are recorded in history only as a sequence of conflicts about mundane affairs, also have relevance in the realm of intellectual discourse. Numerous intellectuals who were faced with the decision aired their views on this matter, so creating a chance for a debate between opposing positions. One of the conversations is to Pope Innocent IV and Emperor Frederick II.

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It occurs between Friedrich. In a pertinent correspondence, the Pope communicates the following to the emperor on May 21, 1239: A creature emerges from the oceans, concealing itself with the paws of bears and the jaws of lions, and utilizing its remaining limbs, resembling a leopard, uttering blasphemous curses against the sacred names, and hurling spears filled with imprecations towards those who reside in the heavens under the protection of God. The creature desires to gnaw at objects with its claws and metallic teeth, and to destroy the whole planet with its powerful feet. For a long time, he has been covertly equipped with battering rams to dismantle the foundations of the Catholic faith. Now, he publicly deploys powerful weapons to attack the spiritual beliefs of the Ishmaelites and vehemently opposes Jesus, who is regarded as the savior of humanity (Houben, 2009, p. 176).

In a letter sent to the kings and princes, Emperor II. Friedrich expressed his sentiments around a month prior to this correspondence in April. He urged the recipients, including beloved prince and all the princes of the world, to refrain from just attributing blame to him, but rather to also consider the church and the collective body of believers. The individuals in question, with their prominent positions and authoritative demeanor, resemble a powerful and intimidating lion. They are characterized as deceitful individuals who have provoked the prophets and shown disrespect. Furthermore, they are described as priests who behave unlawfully and unjustly. (Heinisch, 1968, p. 439).

The rules mentioned in this letter by the emperor pertain to the Roman legal system and include the notion that the kings were bestowed with the sword of secular authority straight from God, bypassing any intermediaries such as the pope or other such authorities. At this juncture, what is being contested is the concept of plenitudo potestatis. Plenitudo potestatis referred to the notion that spiritual authority held a superior position and embraced temporal authority. However, it was impractical for monarchs to relinquish their pursuit of power in accordance with this philosophy. The most profound conflict between the pope and the monarchy occurred during the reigns of King Philippe IV of France (also known as Philippe the Beautiful) and Pope Boniface VIII. The event occurred between Bonifatius. During that period, France had strained relations with the Roman Germanic Empire and England and need funds for

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the war. The Papacy, which has accumulated wealth from the taxation of the populace, disapproves of this circumstance and evades tax payments. However, Pope VIII. Bonifatius, as a staunch advocate of the plenitudo potestatis tori, strongly condemned the king's imposition of taxes on priests without his consent. He sought to prohibit the payment of taxes to laypeople by issuing the Clericis Laicos edict on February 25, 1296. This edict threatened excommunication for those who collected or paid taxes and declared laypeople as adversaries of the clergy. Yes, it does. The source cited is from Wikipedia.de in 2013.

Nevertheless, the king's stance on levying taxes on the affluent pope garnered backing from other factions, leading to Pope VIII. Bonifatius finally retracting his position via the issuance of the Roman Mater Ecclesia decrees in February 1297 and the Esti De Statu decrees in July 1297. In 1301, the tensions resurfaced and escalated to a more severe extent. Indeed, Bishop Bernard Saisset was apprehended and subjected to a trial by the French monarch during the period of strained relations with England, on the basis of allegations of his collaboration with the English. Henry VIII responded with severity to this. Bonifatius responds to the king's actions with the decree of Asculta Fili. However, King Philippe remains steadfast and, in his address to the Etats Generaux, he asserts that he does not acknowledge any authority above him. This statement might be interpreted as asserting that the kingdom has the sword of secular authority independently, without depending on spiritual authority. It suggests that the kingdom will be protected by directly relying on God. Nevertheless, the pope persisted in asserting that the monarch remained subordinate to the pope, using the idea of plenitudo potestatis. At last, King IV of France. Philip VIII enlisted the assistance of Sciarra Colonna, who had a longstanding conflict with the Pope in Rome. He apprehended Bonifatius. Right after that, VIII was rescued with the assistance of the populace. Bonifatius passed away one month later. Successive popes after Pope IV. They declare that they have relinquished several privileges by revoking the decrees imposed on Philippe. (Ağaoğulları, 1997, pages 16-21).

This episode is recorded in history as a significant instance of the king's triumph against the pope. Nevertheless, a crucial aspect of this episode lies in the populace's disposition towards the pope. In reality, it was the inhabitants of that location that

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liberated the Pope from his imprisonment. Securing the backing of individuals in the quest for authority was a crucial endeavor, notwithstanding the absence of a cohesive "people" entity at that period. However, it is crucial to examine feudal modes of production and the categorization of individuals in order to comprehend this era. Currently, there is a growing intensity in the conflict between a pope who aligns his stance with the views of the people, and a King who has full sovereignty, although it is technically at the pinnacle of the system. The feudal lords, who own extensive land holdings, together with people who reside and labor on these grounds, are the primary figures within the social hierarchy. During the feudal era, instead of a centralized system, the management and administration were characterized by a hierarchical yet decentralized structure. The rise and efficacy of the feudal system became apparent with the decline of the centralized state and its incapacity to protect people. This condition subjected the individuals to the authority and control of feudal lords and nobles.

WHAT IS SECULARISM?

By its conventional and traditional interpretation, secularism refers to the division between religious and secular matters, whereby the governance of society is based on laws enacted by parliaments rather than religious principles. It entails allowing individuals to freely exercise their religious beliefs and engage in worship, while leaving matters of faith and conscience to the discretion of the people. Although this statement is accurate, many individuals want to depict secularism as a lack of religious belief or an uncritical adoption of Western values, either due to their own interests or their lack of understanding. Westernization refers to the process of adopting or imitating Western culture, values, and practices. Westernization often denotes the adoption of Western values, perspectives, and cultural practices. Civilization, in essence, refers to the embrace of a logical and progressive perspective on life that is universally shared by all of mankind, rather than being limited to a certain geographical area. This rational and libertarian ideology originated from several ancient civilizations such as Sumer, Egypt, Crete, Greece, Sassanid, and Rome. It underwent two significant periods of humanistic development, namely the

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Renaissance and Reformation, which included the correction of thinking, culture, religion, and the movement towards common sense. Eventually, this ideology found its home in Western Europe.

This civilization emerged as a result of the endeavors of Harun al-Rashid and his sons from the Abbasids during the ninth and tenth centuries. It was particularly influenced by the establishment of universities by the Muslims in Spain, known as the Andalusian Umayyads. These universities offered a wide range of courses, encompassing subjects ranging from philosophy to empirical sciences. During a period when Europe lacked scientific advancements, several Christian priests actively pursued education in Islamic universities in Spain. Ramon Lull (1235-1315), a renowned Christian theologian, was among the foremost figures in his field. Hence, Islam also significantly contributes to the European civilization. Due to its inherent characteristics, westernization should not be seen as a kind of alienation, but rather as a means of enhancing our own development.

Opposition to Western culture stems from the perception of it being synonymous with Christianity, i.e., a society founded upon this religious belief. Western culture is not directly associated with Christianity, meaning it is not directly connected to religion.

If the Christian faith were solely responsible for the development of this civilization, namely if Europe achieved civilization only due to its adherence to Christianity, then other Christian nations around the globe would be expected to possess a degree of civilization on par with that of Europe. The existence of conservative Christian nations in Asia, Africa, and South America contradicts the notion that this is universally true. Now, let us return our attention to the concept of secularism: Within the secular realm, individuals are free to hold their own beliefs without any external interference or coercion. Every person, irrespective of their faith and heritage, have equal entitlements and liberties concerning religious sentiments, convictions, and observance. Individuals have the freedom to hold and practice their own beliefs and religious rituals, and it is not within anyone's power to impose their beliefs or worship practices upon others. He is prohibited from promoting or denouncing any religion via propaganda. Contrary to popular belief, attributing

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personality to religion and granting freedom to the believer's conscience really allows them to wholeheartedly embrace their chosen religion and worship without any constraints. To elucidate this truth, let us examine the antithesis of secularism. The antithesis of secularism is the sharia system.

WHAT IS SHARIA ORDER?

This order signifies that society is regulated in accordance with divine instructions and prohibitions, which were revealed to the Prophet and recorded in the Quran. The Quran contains narratives that depict the actions of past prophets and notable individuals, serving as guidance and exemplary provisions pertaining to matters of religion, worship, interpersonal connections known as munakehat, muamalat, and ukubat.

In addition to the six fundamental beliefs outlined in the Creed and the five essential practices of Islam, it is believed that the Quran contains around two hundred legal principles concerning personal and societal matters. However, the number of verses that directly provide specific judgments does not surpass fifty [1]. They handle broad matters such as marriage, divorce, inheritance, testimony, murder, speeding, drunkenness, adultery, and slander. Due to the restricted and constrained requirements of that era.

The Mecelle included the fundamental premise that "the prayers and rules are subject to change" (it is undeniable that rules vary with the passage of time), and it acknowledged that societal matters would evolve with time. Furthermore, the renowned legal principle, as articulated by Imam Muhammad, a disciple of Imam-i Azam, is that "what is established by tradition is equivalent to what is established by nass (the ruling of the Quran)" [2].

The Quran elucidates the fundamental tenets necessary for the development of an individual's maturity, altruism, tolerance, and morality. The primary objective of worship is to emphasize the moral dimension. Due to the insufficiency of regulations in the Quran and the emergence of new circumstances, several fatwa magazines and fiqh books have been created on diverse issues, each consisting of multiple volumes.

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All of these are creations that have been revised and authored by individuals. In addition, the sources of Islamic law include "qiyas-ı fukaha", which refers to the judgments made by jurists by analogy, and "ijma-i ummah", which refers to the consensus of the people on a new norm.

Hz. The Prophet himself advocated for his companions to use their own judgment and engage in ijtihad when confronted with new circumstances, in accordance with their own perspectives. He sought the perspectives of individuals in his vicinity on various matters and often agreed with the prevailing viewpoint, even if it differed from his own. He demonstrated the significance he attributed to the perspectives and identities of Muslims, as well as the power he bestowed by sometimes seeking the opinions of others, even inside his own camp. For instance, Amr b. He indicated As, who was both the defendant and the plaintiff, and said, "Let us reach a verdict on their case." How is it possible for something to occur when you are present? How can I evaluate? Amr first displayed hesitancy, expressing doubt by saying, but when the Prophet persisted and said "yes, you will be the judge", Amr inquired: "Based on what criteria should I make my judgment?" Inquired. As per the Prophet's statement, if you use your own independent reasoning and arrive at a correct judgment, you will be rewarded with 10 good actions. Conversely, if your decision turns out to be incorrect, you will still be rewarded with one good deed. Over time, the regulations established by legal experts proved insufficient, prompting the development of a more extensive legal framework rooted in tradition, known as "kavanin-i örfiye". Some of them even contradict the tenets of Islam.

As an example, according to these regulations, the Ottoman caliphs-sultans imposed taxes on pork and alcohol on their non-Muslim subjects and allocated the resulting profits towards their military and other governmental requirements. The Mecelle has an article that permits such acts based on the principle of "Necessities make prohibited things permissible" [4]. This implies that duties have the power to transform banned items into permitted ones.

According to common belief, interest is considered haram. However, it is important to clarify that what is really haram is not interest itself, but rather usury, which refers to the practice of charging excessive interest rates. Fatih Sultan Mehmet

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generously contributed twenty-four thousand gold pieces to account for the future price escalation of meat provided to the janissary corps, together with accrued interest. According to an edict issued by Suleiman the Magnificent, it is evident that Fatih the Conqueror founded financial institutions for several objectives. Suleiman the Magnificent also established several financial endowments [5].

During that era, individuals were responsible for establishing the majority of religious regulations and customary legal systems. Different provisions were provided for the same topics in fatwa periodicals, leading to contradictions [6].

The Turks made significant efforts to mitigate these discrepancies and inconsistencies. Celaleddin Melikşah, the son of the renowned Seljuk king Alparslan, endeavored to formulate a comprehensive legislation applicable across all Islamic nations. However, this ambitious endeavor ultimately remained unrealized [7].

SECULARISM AND FREEDOM OF RELIGION

Once more, if we consider the Court's conclusion that its broad interpretation of secularism permits religion to be openly practiced in society, and that the state should not interfere with individual religious beliefs and lifestyles, it follows that religion becomes the foundation of all aspects of social and legal life. It is unavoidable that it will come under the dominance of its norms. Due to the influence of religious ideas and the desire to act in accordance with them, religious norms and ideology will unavoidably shape all aspects of social and cultural life.

NATURE, INTERPRETATION AND COLLECTIVE USE OF FREEDOM OF RELIGION

The essence of establishing a democratic state necessitates a comprehensive analysis of the many domains safeguarded by the freedom of religion. While there may be variations in their quality, fundamental rights and freedoms have a similar foundation and objective. The interconnectedness of basic rights and freedoms

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necessitates a correlation between the freedom of religion and other rights and freedoms when they are collectively exercised. The number 3.

Freedom of religion, or belief, has a foundational and essential significance for a libertarian democratic constitutional state, similar to freedom of thought. Freedom of belief is an essential need for a contemporary constitutional state, both historically and structurally, since it is one of the oldest basic rights. The state's neutrality towards religions has generally evolved with the acknowledgment of freedom of belief. This characteristic has contributed to the state's development in conjunction with other citizen liberties. The attainment of spiritual autonomy, which defines the core of an individual's identity in the realms of religion, politics, or personal life, necessitates the cultivation of collective consciousness. The expressions of public sentiment about the prohibition of abortion and the prohibition of cohabitation between male and female university students have the implication and consequence of enforcing religious legislation.

The link provided is to an article on the website of Milliyet, a Turkish news outlet, titled "Turkey: Co-ed Students".

The extensive range of spiritual expression is derived from the inherent value of human beings, which may be manifested via the liberty to think freely and the entitlement to widespread communication in all aspects of existence. This is also a crucial need for a constitutional state. The unhindered and unrestricted exchange of ideas in the public domain, together with a wide range of perspectives in identifying and resolving issues, serves as a safeguard against the manipulation of facts and highlights the strengths of a democratic constitutional state. The European Court of Human Rights (ECHR) recognizes the role of the right to freedom of expression and access to information in this context. Ensuring the safeguarding of religious freedom would establish the state's impartiality towards ideology and religion, so contributing to the preservation of ideals like democracy that are crucial for the functioning of political systems. The need for sharia is a complex and diverse occurrence, whereby corrupt governments seek to enhance their legitimacy by embracing and using it. Like other forms of spiritual liberties, the realm of religious freedom encompasses several elements and is widely construed in terms of basic rights protection. Article 24 of the

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Constitution fully acknowledges and ensures the right to freedom of religion. The article text encompasses five core rights: freedom of conscience, freedom of religion belief, freedom of thought, freedom to publicly demonstrate religious belief and safeguarding of religious practice (forum externum), and freedom of religious education.

Secularism and Freedom of Religion are included within the framework of basic rights and human rights declarations as a kind of liberal liberty. Within this environment, it is widely acknowledged that it exerts its impact as an indivisible and essential entitlement. For instance, as per the German Federal Constitutional Court, the safeguard proposed by the verbal and systematic analysis of Article 4 of the German Constitution encompasses the practice of living in accordance with one's beliefs, dressing accordingly, and ensuring the religious education of their children as parents. These rights, which safeguard individuals' autonomy in matters of spirituality, also include significant minority rights that contribute to societal harmony and diversity. Given that religions transcend national boundaries and that interference in religious matters may impact even the most isolated religious groups, safeguarding religion at the national level will also foster global harmony. The state's responsibility to safeguard religion against assaults by other entities may be called into doubt when confronted with expressions of anti-religious ideology. Implementing protective measures, such as withholding broadcasting rights from a film considered blasphemous, seizing or prohibiting it, or curbing religious promotion, requires a careful consideration of the balance between freedom of religion and the freedoms of speech and creativity. The European Court of Human Rights (ECHR) provides significant latitude for the member state to assess and determine the relative importance of different factors in this process. The determining factors in these instances include whether there has been any harm caused to religious sentiments due to baseless disdain, if it has incited religious animosity, and whether the action taken is reasonable in relation to the offense.

If the individual aspect of freedom of belief has been surpassed, it is necessary to assess this freedom within the institutional framework of using communal freedom to support the attainment of individual freedom. Individual freedom of thought

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safeguards expressions conveyed by verbal, written, and visual means, such as assertions expressed in speech, writing, and images. When ideas are disseminated by mass media, it surpasses interpersonal communication and activates another right protected by the Constitution, namely the freedom of the press. This freedom is governed by its own legal framework and is accompanied by certain risks and hazards (as stated in Article 28/4-8 of the Constitution). Unlike interpersonal communication, mainstream media is characterized by its consistent and uninterrupted nature. The primary standard for evaluating media statements is the freedom of thought. Furthermore, the institutional framework of the media is contingent upon the freedom of the press, which is subject to certain regulations. This scope specifically includes the authority to decide the format, category, and substance of the publication. Religious institutions have always been an integral part of the collective aspect that defines freedom of belief. This approach ensures the support of individuals' freedom of belief and the effective implementation of religious freedom. Can religious groups, functioning as private law legal entities like as organizations, invoke the protection of freedom of religion? The current discourse is on the correlation between personal religious liberties and organizational religious liberties.

THE MEANING OF FREEDOM OF RELIGION AND AREA OF PROTECTION

The essential inquiry about the meaning of freedom of religion is whether the society in issue will have its own definition fully acknowledged, or whether an impartial criterion will be enforced externally. The decisive factor in this case is neither the religious faith of the individual exercising their basic right, nor the interpretation of the religious community. Hence, a community's self-professed adherence to a religion and its identification as a religious community does not automatically warrant the invocation of freedom of religion for itself and its members. The ECHR has adopted a moderate and balanced approach. Hence, it is essential to acknowledge the individual's own comprehension as a fundamental basis. However, it is equally important to establish certain external prerequisites. Therefore, it is necessary to have at least one religion that can be clearly recognized. Hence, a religious perspective is

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safeguarded if it has a certain level of believability, gravity, context, and significance. The matter at hand pertains to formal characteristics. The safeguarding of Article 9 cannot be contingent upon the religious validity or rationale of the perspective.

The European Court of Human Rights (ECHR) defers the resolution of whether "Scientology" qualifies as a religion to home legal frameworks, following the concept of subsidiarity. For instance, in Germany, only conduct rooted in religion and belief is included under the scope of this freedom. The perspective that serves as the foundation for such conduct must be acknowledged as a religion based on its spiritual essence and manifestation, the actuality of contemporary existence, cultural heritage, and the overall comprehension of theology. From the perspective of the constitution, the understanding of human existence and the link between humans and the physical and non-physical aspects of reality, as well as the fundamental living values derived from this understanding, are protected based on religious beliefs and worldview. The European Court of Human Rights (ECHR) refrains from providing a rigid definition of the notion of religion due to pragmatic considerations. This freedom encompasses not just established faiths, but also emerging religious movements. Furthermore, the court assesses belief systems such as Krishna belief, Jehovah's Witness, and Divine Light Center, in addition to fundamental belief systems like monotheistic faiths and Buddhism, within the purview of Article 9. This liberty safeguards three domains of endeavor: cognition and moral principles (thought), articulation (verbal expression), and conduct. The concept of intrinsic freedom of religion, also known as forum internum, encompasses the initial action of thinking and safeguards the ability to accept and modify religious beliefs. Within this framework, faith pertains to the internal perspective that individuals have on God and the existence after death. The scope of freedom of belief is broad; it encompasses more than simply religious beliefs. Additionally, it encompasses philosophies such as atheism, pacifism, materialism, monism, and pantheism. Conscience refers to an individual's cognizance of ethical principles and the compelling factors that bind them. The basic right to freedom of conscience, which safeguards an individual's unalterable beliefs, is a principle of significant constitutional importance, ensuring the protection of subjective rights. The second component of internal freedom of religion, known as forum internum, is the expression of religious conviction (conscience and belief) or the communication of

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judgments derived from it. The principle of safeguarding freedom of belief prevents the state from subjectively assessing, based on its own standards, the legitimacy of a religious entity as per its own convictions first. However, a specificity verification is permitted in the second phase. Therefore, the primary concern of the court is not the direct impact of religious efforts on public opinion, but rather safeguarding individuals against the state's unwarranted encroachment on their freedom of religion in certain instances. Within this framework, the freedom of religion guarantees immunity when it comes to declining a crucial blood transfusion that may save a person's life, all due to religious convictions. Nevertheless, within this framework, the freedom to govern one's life based on religious beliefs should neither serve as a valid excuse for disregarding the established laws, nor should it provide a means to evade punishment for engaging in unlawful activities. Indeed, the need to pay the tax that funds military expenses does not infringe upon freedom of conscience, and there is no entitlement to evade payment for the portion of the energy bill that corresponds to the electricity generated by nuclear power plants.

External religious freedom, also known as *forum externum*, safeguards the individual's entitlement to publicly express and behave in accordance with their religious beliefs, including religious worship and study. Both negative and positive religious freedom are safeguarded. It safeguards the liberty to abstain from holding a religious conviction, to refrain from disclosing one's religious beliefs, and to remain apathetic towards all faiths. The European Court of Human Rights (ECHR) ruled against Turkey, stating that the need to disclose one's religious affiliation on the identification card violates Article of the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR). The investigation determined that it breached the provisions of Article 9. However, there is a requirement.

Both the Constitutional Court and the Council of State have rendered unfavorable rulings that infringe upon the freedom of religion. Nevertheless, negative religious freedom has notably robust safeguards. Mandating the disclosure of religious affiliation infringes against the principle of negative religious freedom without any room for exceptions. For instance, the need for a member of parliament or a witness in court to swear a religious oath infringes against fundamental freedom.

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In Turkey, the primary concern about freedom of religion mostly stems from the enforcement of worship practices that restrict religious liberty. In this particular environment, pressure and coercion are used by both governmental officials and private individuals. Challenges also emerge in the domain of external religious liberty. Freedom includes the display of religious symbols and the observance of religious dietary restrictions. The European Court of Human Rights (ECHR) ruled that the ban on headscarves at universities is in accordance with the ECHR. Furthermore, the court determined that the expulsion of a student who refused to take off their hijab during a physical education session did not violate Article 9. Please see the publication by Vural H. S. titled "Constitutional Guarantee for Freedom of Religion in Turkey" on page 294.

The European Court of Human Rights (ECHR) has issued a ruling against Turkey, declaring that the need to reveal one's religious affiliation on the identity card is in violation of Article of the ECHR. This article safeguards the right to freedom of religion, including the right to not divulge one's religious beliefs. In the case of *Işık v. TUR*, No. 21924/05, the court concluded that there was a violation of Article 9.

According to the Constitutional Court, while registering in the civil registration, the declaration of an individual's religious views and convictions does not follow the specific requirements outlined in the Constitution. However, it is only essential to provide facts pertaining to the individual's particular circumstances, matters of public concern, maintenance of public order, and societal needs. This prerequisite is mandatory. "It does not exhibit any correlation with its intrinsic attributes and compulsion." (E. 1995/17, K. 1995/16, K.t. 21.06.1995).

The Council of State has approved the court orders that rejected the request to nullify the administrative decisions that refused to include the religious denominations "Bahai," "Sky-God," and "Jehovah's Witness" in the category of religions. To get information on rulings, please see Erdem Karahanoğulları Ö.'s article titled "Freedom of Religion, Conscience and Thought in the Decisions of the Council of State."

The denial by the prison administration to accommodate the dietary request of a Buddhist inmate for a vegetarian lunch is a violation of Article 9. However, not every religiously inspired movement is a protected religious activity. The activity must

possess a characteristic association with the relevant religion or worldview. The constitutional guarantee of religious freedom does not clearly specify whether actions that are simply preliminary or supportive, such as economic activity, are included. To avail oneself of protection, the conduct must not be only driven by business interests and must not stem from exclusively personal motives. Hence, there must exist a fundamental and tangible link between action and faith. For instance, the act of selling food products at a religious gathering does not fall within the safeguard of religious liberty. Actions driven by economic motives and disguised with religious elements, such as soliciting substantial funds from certain religious communities, are likewise excluded from this protected domain.

Similarly, the inclination to be buried in one's own land is not a religious ritual. at a similar event, the Council of State invalidated the Council of Ministers' decision on the interment of former Minister Y. Özal at the Süleymaniye Mosque Cemetery, as per his will. The number is 46. As per the 10th Chamber of the Council of State, our legislation does not provide the Council of Ministers the power to create a "mausoleum" or permit burial in the mosque cemetery. In contrast, legislation No. 677, enacted in 1930 and referred to as a "revolutionary law" under Article 153 of the Constitution, demolished the existing tombs and imposed penalties, including fines and imprisonment, on anybody who attempted to reinstate them. The decision of the Council of Ministers to allow Yusuf Bozkurt Özal to be buried in the mosque cemetery is in violation of Law No. 677, particularly in terms of power.

Not only is individual religious freedom preserved, but communal religious freedom is also safeguarded. The ability to create a religious community is included by the right to freedom of religion. As per the European Court of Human Rights (ECHR), this right encompasses the entitlement of the religious community to assert its legal status under national legislation.

The case of Congregation of Jehovah's Witnesses v. AUT, No. 40825/98, was brought to the European Court of Human Rights (ECHR). There are three significant rulings of the Supreme Court on this matter. In the first instance, Jehovah's Witness was classified as "a religion or sect". In the second instance, it was referred to as "Jehovah's Witness Sect". In the third instance (as per the Criminal General Board

decision), it was labeled simply as a "sect" (with a dissident member being described as such). For further details, refer to Tümer G.'s article titled "Jehovah's Witnesses Movement and Whether It Is a Religion". The aspect of freedom of association is also considered in this context. The religious community's administrative autonomy is included by the collective freedom of religion. The entity has the ability to govern its internal structure and make decisions on membership eligibility. The significance and relevance of the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) in governing the interactions between the government and religious groups is progressively growing. The fundamental concept at hand is the notion of state neutrality:

Based on the survey conducted by Konda Research Company for TESEV on 22-23 September, approximately 50.6 percent of the population expressed the view that secularism should be preserved in its current form as stated in the Constitution. Meanwhile, around two-fifths of the respondents believed that secularism should be maintained, but with the condition that the state maintains an equal distance from all religions. He believes that it should be clearly stated. 10% of individuals advocate for the total elimination of secularism from the constitution.

The link provided is:
<http://fotoanaliz.hurriyet.com.tr/galeridetay.aspx?cid=62865&rid=4369&p=1&hid=219863> November 22, 2012

The state has a responsibility to be unbiased while creating laws and when dealing with various populations and belief systems. The state's duty to remain unbiased may encounter some constraints in situations of intercultural conflicts. Individuals are not obligated to embrace a distinct cultural identity as their own. The area of gender equality encompasses several instances, such as the coerced marriage of young girls, the infliction of mutilations during religious ceremonies, the denial of educational opportunities for females, honor murders, and the imposition of restrictions on freedom of thought. These practices, rooted in religious or cultural beliefs, are deemed unacceptable and must not be accepted. The need of impartiality serves as the foundation for the notion of equal treatment. The Constitutional Court's ruling on Abrahamic Religions, E. 1986/11, K. 1986/26, Kt., serves as a model judgment for upholding the norm of equality in the realm of religious freedom.

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The Supreme Court of Appeals Criminal General Assembly, in its decision dated 26.5.1986 and numbered E: 1985/9, K: 1986/293, declared that the Republic of Turkey is a secular state. It emphasized that a secular state maintains neutrality towards religions and does not have an official religious status. The Republic of Turkey (T.R.) adheres to a secular state structure and upholds the fundamental concept of not endorsing any official religion. He asserted that in his jurisdiction, the power to determine whether a person's religious belief qualifies as a religion or not does not rest with the government or any of its branches. He emphasized that all forms of religious beliefs are protected by the Constitution, including the religious perspective and thought system of Jehovah's Witnesses, which is consequently safeguarded by constitutional provisions.

The financial assistance offered by the government must align with the notion of state neutrality. The Eighth Chamber of the Council of State rendered a decision in 2005 regarding this matter. The decision of the Administrative Court, which dismissed the lawsuit seeking to invalidate the transaction concerning the denial of the Protestant church's request for free water usage, was overturned. The grounds for overturning the decision were that "religious disparities in service provision cannot be taken into account". The German Federal Constitutional Court has granted approval for the state of Brandenburg to provide assistance for Jewish communal life. Conversely, the Presidency of Religious Affairs denied the request made by a group of citizens to offer religious services to Alevis as a public service, grant cemeteries the status of religious institutions, and appoint individuals approved by Alevis as public officials. The Presidency justified its decision by asserting that the services it provides are non-sectarian and inclusive, ensuring equal access for all individuals. The rejection was based on the legal impossibility of granting cemeteries the status of a place of worship, as determined by legislation and judicial decisions. Additionally, it was deemed inappropriate to grant privileges to individuals seeking public office based on their sects, dispositions, religious beliefs, and practices. The case seeking to invalidate the mentioned transaction was dismissed by the ruling of the Ankara Administrative Court, a judgment that was subsequently upheld by the Council of State.

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The decision made by Deputy Prime Minister Bekir Bozdağ to address the requests of Alevi about cem homes is a flagrant violation of the principle of equal treatment, as outlined in the Revolutionary Laws. Recep Tayyip Erdoğan, the former prime minister, explicitly said that the individuals in question are unequivocally identified as Zarathustra, so categorizing them as terrorists. According to his statement, he diminished the importance of a certain religious belief, <http://www.ozgurdurum.net/Siyaseterdogan-bu-teroristler-zerdust-110087.html> (21.11.2012).

Recep Tayyip Erdoğan's assertion that the legislation permitting the shutdown of lodges and zawiya should be revoked is inconsistent with the existing legal framework. With the exception of Article 3 of Law No. 677, which pertains to the walls of Dervish Lodges, Lodges and Tombs, and the prohibition and elimination of specific titles, as well as the law regarding the prohibition of certain attire, our legislation lacks regulations that explicitly define a place of worship and specify the necessary criteria for a location to be recognized as a place of worship. Conversely, the Act enforces legal repercussions on the notion of a house of worship. Indeed, according to Zoning Law No. 3194, the definition of "building" includes buildings that are used for religious worship. Conversely, Article 153 of the Turkish Penal Code categorizes the destruction, damage, or vandalism of houses of worship, their annexes, and their valuables as criminal offenses. The "place of worship," as mandated by Law No. 3194, necessitates the allocation of a designated area for construction during the zoning regulation process. It is safeguarded by the Turkish Penal Code and encompasses places of worship for all faiths and belief systems, without any form of discrimination. The notion that granting Cem houses the status of places of worship is legally impossible contradicts the principle of legislative authority's generality, as it excludes these places from the legal texts mentioned. Additionally, it violates the principle of impartiality by determining the legitimacy of the belief content of a religious community, which is a result of current life and cultural tradition. The state is obligated to maintain religious and ideological neutrality. This means that definitions used should adhere to the standards of protecting basic rights effectively. These definitions should be as inclusive as possible, applicable to everyone, and not influenced by any religious or ideological perspective. The Government's rationale for

including extra article 2 in the aforementioned Law is to guarantee that individuals of various religious affiliations and belief systems may freely practice their religious worship within the context of freedom of religion and conscience.

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To ascertain the legitimacy of practicing a religion or worldview in a certain situation, it is necessary to provide clear definitions of these notions within a tangible context. In the case of the closure of the "Çankaya Cemevi Built Association", the Ankara 16th Civil Court, in its last hearing on 20.22.20012, deemed the decision of the 7th Civil Chamber of the Supreme Court of Appeals to be lawful. The Supreme Court had ordered the closure of the association on the basis that the cemevi is not a place of worship. The court affirmed that the cem house is indeed a place of worship, supporting its previous decision.

CAN THERE BE SHARIA RULES APPLICABLE TO ALL MUSLIMS?

Such a thing is almost unattainable. This inability emerges from an undisclosed cause to those desiring sharia. The motivation and necessity to compile these universal principles emerged during the initial period of the Abbasid dynasty. The Abbasid caliph, al-Mansur (reigned from 754 to 775), requested Imam Malik b. Enes (lived from 712 to 795) to gather the legal regulations and provide his personal viewpoint. Consequently, Imam Malik authored "al-Muwatta," a comprehensive work encompassing Maliki fiqh. Harun al-Rashid, who became the caliph in 786, visited Imam Malik and proposed the idea of publicly displaying his book at the Kaaba, allowing others to read it and promoting unity in religious practices. Imam Malik responded negatively, advising against engaging in such an action. Competent jurists located around the nation render judgments that align with the specific needs of their respective jurisdictions. Despite the varying choices they provide, all of them are accurate. Pay heed to their advice. He intended to express [8].

Currently, there are several Islamic sects in existence, however historically, there have been a total of seventy-two sects. The individuals are categorized into three

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distinct groups: Ahl al-Sunnah, Shia, and Khawarij. Three of them, excluding Ahl al-Sunnah, possess distinct fiqh, which refers to independent legal frameworks. The following items are: 1- The sect known as "imamiye", "isnâ aseriye" or "Caferiye" is now prevalent in Iran. 2- The "Zaydiye" sect, belonging to the Shia branch, is prevalent in Southern Arabia and the Yemen area. 3 - The "Ibâziye" sect, widely followed by the people of Tanzania (Zanzibar), is regarded an external sect.

The remaining four Sunni sects, namely the "Hanafi sect" prevalent in Turkey, Jordan, and partially in Syria, the "Hanbali sect" (in the form of Wahhabism) prevalent in Saudi Arabia, and the "Shafi'i sect" prevalent in Egypt. The "Mâliki sect", prevalent in North Africa and Sudan, also has several fiqhs. Each originator of the seven legal systems (fiqh) has the belief that their set of Sharia principles is the most accurate, and the cultures adhering to these systems think that their chosen path aligns best with Sharia and Islam. Given the current circumstances, which of the seven distinct fiqh systems would be deemed the authoritative sharia norm and universally implemented throughout all Islamic communities? Evidently, this work is more complex and challenging than it seems... In the latter part of the previous century, research was conducted in the Ottoman nation to seek a resolution to this intricate and multifaceted predicament. Âlî Pasha proposed the adaptation of the French civil code to Turkish society, whereas Cevdet Pasha recommended the preparation of a law by gathering previous fatwas and jurisprudence. Ultimately, the proposition put forward by Cevdet Pasha was approved, leading to the establishment of a committee with him as its leader. Their compilation included gathering antiquated legal principles and regulations, resulting in the creation of a comprehensive body of law consisting of 1851 articles known as "Mecelle-i Ahkam-ı Adliye." This compilation was structured as an introductory section followed by sixteen volumes, each containing specific topics.

The objective of this endeavor was to consolidate the principles of the science of fiqh in order to address the demands of the current era and the evolving everyday need.

This majallah, which adheres to the teachings of the Hanafi sect, cannot be regarded as a comprehensive legal code. Furthermore, this regulation lacks rules pertaining to family law matters such as marriage, divorce, alimony, lineage, personal

rights, inheritance, wills, and foundations, all of which are significant aspects of civil law. Without a question, Mecelle is a result of extensive work and effort and a significant phase in our legislative history. However, the era of putting it into practice has long gone. The divergent legal frameworks established by different sects have resulted in the fragmentation of Islamic communities instead of consolidating them under a unified sharia system. In contemporary society, individuals are more inclined to embrace shared behaviors and regulations across several domains. Customs union, communications union, common market, shared sports activities, and other similar arrangements. Instances such as these provide as evidence for this claim. Passport visas have been eliminated in several nations.

This clearly demonstrates that the exceptional leader Atatürk attained the utmost reverence for religion with the implementation of the idea of secularism. He did not oppose religion; rather, he opposed those who used religion for personal gain. These individuals, living in lodges, relied on the people for sustenance. He also disapproved of the religious sect leaders, who resorted to superstitious practices such as tying rags to shrines and seeking assistance from the deceased. Additionally, he held disdain for witches. He was aware that the only sect in Islam was the way delineated by the Prophet, and that Islam emphasized the essence rather than the outward appearance. We want to provide an illustration of the caliphs who comprehended Islam in such a manner.

Ömer b., an Umayyad caliph, received some correspondence from his governor in Egypt, notifying him of a significant decline in tribute and jizya revenues. This decline was attributed to the conversion of a majority of Christians in the region to Islam, as they sought to evade taxes. Consequently, the governor recommended that these individuals be subjected to the same taxation as before. The Caliph expressed his awareness of the individual's incompetence, yet, due to the absence of a more suitable candidate and the individual's lack of thievery, the Caliph appointed him as governor. God exists. The Prophet was not sent as a tax collector. He sent individuals to safeguard them from malevolence and cultivate their moral character. The author explicitly said that Muslims should not be subjected to the collection of tribute or jizya.

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Once again, the governor of Khorasan, who served under the caliph, expressed to him that the people residing in this region are embracing the Islamic faith, however they have not undergone the practice of circumcision. "He wrote that we should collect tribute and jizya from those who have not undergone circumcision," he said. The Caliph addressed him, saying, "May God Almighty, Hz." He did not appoint Muhammad as a circumciser. Anyone who holds the belief in the oneness of God and the prophethood of His Messenger is considered a Muslim. In response, he said that it is not permissible to collect Haraj and jizya from Muslims. The user's text is "[9]".

Similar to the caliphs of the Umayyad and Abbasid eras, the Ottoman caliph-sultans did not involve themselves in religious matters and instead entrusted them to the Islamic sheikhs. Nevertheless, they would get the desired fatwa from the Shaykh al-Islams. Put simply, the caliph-sultan was subordinate to the sultan, rather than to the fiqh and the jurist. However, the caliph-sultan was accountable to the fiqh and the faqih, which refer to the legal system and the jurist, respectively. Indeed, the Ottoman Sultans had the ability to acquire fatwas at their discretion from the sheikh al-Islams, who held the greatest positions of authority in matters of Islamic jurisprudence and justice. This enabled them to arrange for the execution of their own sons and brothers.

Sultan Ibrahim, the ruler of a period referred to as the "Sable Era" due to his affinity for fur, earned the nickname "Sable Age" and had a habit of adorning his beard with pearls and generously showering his subjects with money. The ruler, who was manipulated by Cinci Hodja, a person known for his control over the palace women and administrators, had his grand vizier executed by strangulation using a rope from the garden well. This was because the vizier failed to prevent the horse carriages, which annoyed the ruler, from freely roaming the streets of Istanbul. Additionally, the ruler appointed one of the palace women as the Governor of Damascus.

Amidst the escalating events, the intellectuals and prominent figures of that day deposed him and appointed his six-year-old son, Mehmed the Fourth, as the caliph. To ensure the death of Crazy Ibrahim by the executioner Kara Ali, the six-year-old caliph was compelled to sign a strongly worded "hatti hümayun" under the authority of the sheikh al-Islam, despite his lack of comprehension of its significance. Based on the aforementioned underlying causes and the provided instances, the establishment of a

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universally applicable sharia system for all Islamic communities has proven unattainable. In order to address the inadequacies of the Qur'anic provisions in regulating the evolving needs, relationships, rights, and responsibilities of society over time, additional rules such as ietihad, qiyas, and customary law have been introduced by various individuals. Has been created. Within a secular framework, the laws enacted by duly appointed committees of national legislatures, chosen by the populace, adhere to both religious principles, individual rights, and societal interests.

The emergence of various exploitations of sharia and caliphateism may be attributed to the inadequate explanation of the actual essence and objectives of Islam over the course of centuries, which led to the propagation of several superstitious beliefs under the guise of religion. Islam acquired its authentic character via the adoption of secularism throughout the era of the republic.

The inconsistencies in the comprehension of religion in our nation stem from the conflation of religion and mundane matters. Religious matters: faith, devotion, permissible and forbidden. Others pertain to matters of the world. It is important to avoid mistaking them for one another. This comprehension does not imply atheism, but rather entails the distinction between the entitlements and obligations of God, individuals, and the government, which is the essence of secularism. If all aspects are included under the scope of religion, inevitable complications will occur. Indeed, in the past, practices such as shaving the beard and mustache, donning pants, a cap or fez, a tie, or a shirt, using utensils like a fork and spoon, dining at a table with separate bowls, undergoing medical examinations, receiving dental fillings, applying perfume, and cooking on an alcohol burner were often seen. The act of verbalizing disrupted activities like as consuming food and beverages, receiving medical treatment, and getting dressed.

These issues pertain to one's well-being and convenience, rather than being religious in nature. In order to foster a secure and prosperous environment for our nation's development, it is crucial to educate capable, tolerant, and unbiased clergy who are not affiliated with any political party. It is equally important to ensure that they serve as role models to the public through their exemplary moral conduct.

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Europe's dominance stems from its prioritization of science, the absence of church interference in societal matters, and the intelligent, sophisticated, and tolerant nature of its clergy.

Limitation

The limitations of the research are limited to the scope of the subject in the light of world literature and data. The research was conducted by limiting closely related authors and literature topics. Restricted to literature review.

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Publication ethics of our university's relevant regulations; It is a national-based scientific study that aims to ensure that scientific research and publications are carried out in accordance with basic principles such as honesty, openness, objectivity, respect for the findings and creations of others, and works to achieve this, aiming at these principles in the field of relevant sciences.

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Cevdet Pasha expresses the necessity of determining the rules that can be applied in all Islamic communities with the following words: “It is very difficult to comprehend the subjects of fiqh and to reach their depth. For a while, jurists and virtuous people of the time were brought together to cover the problems of Hanafi fiqh and published works such as "Tatar Haniye" and "Fetâvây-i Cihangîriye", but the details of all fiqh problems and sectarian disagreements could not be included in this work. Look. Mecelle, the edition mentioned in the previous note, pp. 2.

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